

Figure 23: marmans in an 8x8 vāstu, PI 8.18c-28b.

	marman name, symbol	number in this vāstu
vaṃśa	5	
	vajra	28
	sandhi	16
	pada	24
rajju	16	
	saṃpuṭa	32
	triśūla	4
	maṇibandha	8
sirā	20	
	svastika	0

